

**“UMUMIY O’RTA TA’LIM MAKTABLARINING 9-SINF
O’QUVCHILARIGA INDUKSION HISOBLAGICH QURILMASIDAN
ELEKTROTEXNIK STEND YASASH VA O’QITISH METODIKASI”**

Abduxakim Nigmatovich Abdullayev

t.f.n., PhD., O’zbekiston milliy pedagogika universiteti “Texnologiya va professional ta’lim metodikasi” kafedrası dotsenti.

Rustamova Rayhona Hasanboy qizi

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Annotatsiya: Kirish, mavzuning dolzarbligi, maqsadi va vazifalarini aniqlash, adabiyotlar bilan ishlash ilmiy yangiliklar bilan tanishish, elektrostend tayyorlash.

Kalit so’zlar: Universal elektrostend, qurilish materiallaridan foneks, yog’och, ushlagich, bolt, gayka, mix, shrup, konselyar pichog’i, o’lchov metri, sirkul, elektr istemolchilari va Induksion hisoblagich.

Аннотация: Введение, определение актуальности темы, цели и задачи, работа с литературой, ознакомление с научными новостями, подготовка электрического стенда.

Ключевые слова: Универсальная электрическая подставка, строительные материалы: телефон, дерево, держатель, болт, гайка, гвоздь, шуруп, малярная лента, рулетка, компас, электропотребители и индукционный измеритель.

Annotation: Introduction, determining the relevance of the topic, goals and objectives, working with literature, getting acquainted with scientific news, preparing an electric stand.

Key words: Universal electrical stand, construction materials: phonex, wood, holder, bolt, nut, nail, screw, masking tape, tape measure, compass, electrical consumers and induction meter.

Natijalar:

Umumta’lim maktablarida texnologiya fanini o’qitish jarayonida o’quvchilarda 9-sinfda induksion hisoblagich qurilmasidan elektrotexnik stend yasash va o’qitish metodikasini o’qitishda kreativ yondashuvga oid ma’lumotlarni tadqiq qilish. Fan bo’yicha mashg’ulotlarni tashkil qilishda kasbiy shakllanish texnologiyasiga oid metodik tavsiyalar ishlab chiqish. Shu muammoni hal etishda ta’lim muassasadagi bitiruv malaka ishini to’g’ri yo’naltirib natijaga erishish maqsadga muvofiqdir.

Mashina detallari, mashina mexanizmlar nazariyasi, amaliy mexanika, gidravlika, elektrotexnika, materiallar qarshiligi, texnologiya, fizika kabi fanlarda

laboratoriya va amaliy darslar mavjudligi, darsni moddiy texnika bazasini takomillashtirishga olib keladi. Bu esa holatdan chiqish masalasini o'rtga qo'yadi. Uni xalq etishda iqtidorli o'quvchilardan foydalanib, ularga mavzuga, fanga doir maket va model yaratishni o'rgatish muammoni yechimi bo'ladi. Maxalliy xom ashyolardan **universal elektrostendni** xavola qilamiz. Oldin oddiy fanerada tayyorlab olib keyin foneksda asosiy stend yasaladi.

Bunda quyidagi ishlar bajariladi:

1. Elektr zanjirlari uchun universal stendni modellashtirish bo'yicha sohada olib borilayotgan tadqiqot bo'yicha adabiyotlar bilan tanishish
2. Tadqiqot bo'yicha izlanishlarning bosqich va usullari bilan tanishib chiqish.
3. Tadqiqotning maqsad va vazifalari hamda qo'yilgan masalaga ijodiy yondashishni o'rganish
4. «Elektr zanjirlari uchun universal stendni modellashtirish»ni o'rganish.
5. AKT dan model yaratishda foydalanish.

Elektr tokini hosil qiluvchi va uning oqib o'tishini ta'minlovchi qurilmalar yig'indisi elektr zanjirini tashkil qiladi. Om qonuni va Kirxgof qonunlari asosida stendni yig'ishni boshlaymiz. Kerakli bo'ladigan qurilmalarga: o'tkazgichlar, elektro'lchash asboblari, transformator, kondensator, yarim o'tkazgichlar, elektr dvigatel, vklyuchatellar, klemmalar va qurilish ashyolari (1-rasm).

(1-rasm).

Qoralama stend

Induksion hisoblagich

texnologi xarita

T/r	Ish ketma-ketligi	Ish eskizi yoki texnik rasmi	jihaz va moslamalar
1	qurilish materiallaridan foneks,yog'och, ushlagich,bolt,gayka,mix, shrup va elektr istemolchilari olinadi	<p style="text-align: center; color: red;">foneks</p> <div style="border: 1px solid red; width: 100px; height: 50px; margin: 0 auto;"></div> <p style="text-align: center; color: red;">shruplar</p>	<p>qurilish materiallaridan foneks,yog'och,ushlagich, bolt,gayka,mix,shrup,kon selyar pichog'i,o'lchov metri,sirkul elektr istemolchilari va Induksion hisoblagich.</p>

		<p>istemolchi va simlar</p>	
2	<p>tayanch karkas tayyorlanib elektr istemolchilar maxkamlab olinadi oldi va orqa tomonidan maxkamlangan</p>	<p>orqa tarafidan mahkamlanish</p>	<p>qurilish materiallaridan foneks,yog'och,ushlagich, bolt,gayka,mix,shrup,kon selyar pichog'i,o'lchov metri,sirkul va elektr istemolchilari</p>

3	<p>tayyor elektrostend elektr manbaga ulanib ishga tushiriladi</p>		
		<p>tayyor elektrostend</p>	

Muhokama:

Elektrostendni tayyorlashda texnik vositalar noutbuk, elektr o'lchash asboblari, simlar, qurilish materiallari, radio detallar, mehnat ish qurollari va hokazolar tanlab olinadi. Fanlar kesimidagi maket va modellarni to'la elektr avtomatlashtirish universal, maqsadga muvofiqdir. Chunki dars jarayonida maket, modelni tok manbaiga ulab uni harakatga keltirib ko'rgazmali tushuntirish, ta'lim sifatiga katta ta'sir qiladi.

Xulosa:

Yuqoridagilarni amalga oshirish uchun talabani nazariy va amaliy bilim, ko'nikma, malakasini shakllantirish muvaffaqiyat garovidir. Bunda quyidagi ishlar ketma-ketligi bajariladi. Masalan mavzuga oid **o'tkazgichlarni ulash usullari** modelini yaratishda: qurilish materiallari, elektr-radio detallar, kabel simlar, tanlab oladi.

Sistemada bir xil tok va kuchlanishni ta'minlash uchun transformatoridan foydalanib montaj qilamiz (4-rasm).

4-rasm. O'zgaruvchan tok transformatori.

Elektrodvigatelga doir muammoni hal qilishda zanjirdagi tok va kuchlanishga mos elektr dvigatel tanlab sxemaga montaj qilamiz. Shunday qilib to'liq stend montaj qilindi. undan laboratoriya va amaliyot darslarida foydalanish mumkin.

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